

On the Service Probability of MEC-enabled Beyond 5G Systems supporting 3GPP Location Services

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Abstract—Location-informed network management will play an instrumental role in MEC-enabled next generation-RAN (NG-RAN) infrastructures where mobile users are looking to offload local computation tasks to the network edge/cloud continuum. This paper derives exact and approximate expressions on the joint distribution of *direct distances* from a tagged mobile UE towards two target MEC hosts, as well as the resulting MEC Service probability, conditioned on location knowledge provided by the Location Management Function (LMF). The derived expressions are used to plot numerical results and extract measurable insights on how the presence of an additional MEC host increases the probability of successful task offloading to the MEC infrastructure, or how the seamless mobility of MEC apps across MEC hosts relaxes the requirement of attaining a maximum (direct) distance from MEC hosts.

Index Terms—5G/6G, multi-access edge computing, location-informed network management, MEC service probability

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent technological advances and standardization efforts towards 6G, enable intelligent, fine-grained and location-informed network management decisions to address emerging service requirements and novel types of user equipment (UE). On the one hand, ultra-contextual, delay-sensitive and computation-hungry services, such as vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communications, extended reality (XR) apps, real-time digital twins (DTs), and AI-driven computer vision (CV) tasks, have attracted surge of interest to enable seamless control of critical processes/assets of the physical realm. Such services increasingly rely on precise location information to determine the optimal blend of edge computing resources [1]. On the other hand, the 6G ecosystem encompasses a wide range of UE types, which complicate the network management pipeline across the different network segments and slices.

Accurate positioning in Beyond 5G (B5G) networks is made possible by an ever-increasing suite of reference signals and measurement capabilities. Depending on the UE state (e.g., connected, idle) and the requirements of the particular network application (NetApp), 3GPP provisions for Positioning Reference Signals (PRS), Sidelink (SL), Sounding Reference Signals (SRS), Synchronization Signals (SS), Channel State Information (CSI), and other types of Positioning Beacons [2]. Besides, after Rel. 18 of the 3GPP 5GS, the UEs and the next-generation radio access network (NG-RAN) [3] are equipped

with advanced capabilities for measuring: a) their *distance* from a target network node, e.g., by measuring the reference signal received power (RSRP), reference signal strength indicator (RSSI), time difference (TD), timing advance (TA), b) their *angle* with respect to a target network node and reference direction, e.g., by measuring the Angle-of-Arrival (AoA), relative time of arrival (RTOA), multi round-trip times (mRTT), TA and TD per antenna port, and c) the *network load*, e.g., by measuring the channel occupancy ratio, channel busy ratio. Critical enabler to this end is the integration of massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) capabilities, beamforming and recently, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS), that not only improve data throughput and spectral efficiency but also enhance spatial resolution by distinguishing between multipath signals and line-of-sight components [4].

Moving one step further, 3GPP has recently outlined the 3GPP Location Services (LCS) framework that separates localization functionalities across different entities to modularize location-informed decisions while maintaining interoperability with both 3GPP and non-3GPP systems [5]. Key component of the LCS framework is the Location Management Function (LMF) that, among others, can i) consume positioning information on the coordinates of installed base stations (BSs), e.g., by pulling such information from the Operations, Administration and Maintenance (OAM) subsystem and converting it to the Earth-Centered, Earth-Fixed (ECEF) format whenever necessary, ii) centrally manage reference signal transmissions and/or measurement patterns across the NG-RAN, iii) perform local inference in line with service-specific localization errors by employing advanced multi-lateration and/or other non-standardized measurement fusion technologies, such as fingerprinting, and iv) expose such location estimates to external parties via the Network Exposure Function (NEF). The UE and NG-RAN measurements are processed by the LMF and communicated to authorized consumers only (e.g., UEs, over-the-top service providers, other network functions). As highlighted also in Section 6 of [5] and in [7], such measurements can also be processed by the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) to estimate long-term network topology statistics.

Either prior, or during the measurement phase, the UE initiates its edge computing task, (e.g., for rendering XR outputs, or offloading local camera feeds for 6D object tracking, or communicating telemetry data for digital twins) and evaluates its proximity to nearby MEC hosts that can accommodate its MEC-empowered application instances [6]. Accordingly, the session management function (SMF) and user plane function (UPF) instances are triggered to establish the local traffic

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breakout towards the target MEC host(s). During this phase, the UE can pull from the LMF location information to better assess the set of target MEC hosts within its proximity. This phase does not necessarily require full data on the locations of all entities involved in the service function chain from the UE to the MEC host, e.g., serving antenna BSs, MEC host or UE location; yet, depending on the information available to the LMF, which typically originates from different sources, it should assume only partial information and in most of the cases, be adapted with respect to the error margins suitable for the target MEC service. Current literature includes a plethora of works and studies on how to offload edge-intensive traffic to the networked edge/cloud continuum [1], [4]; however, it lacks of benchmark models that enable the UEs to leverage location information available at the B5G core (LMF), e.g., by processing 3GPP-compatible measurements made available by the NG-RAN, to infer on the target MEC hosts within proximity. Accordingly, we summarize our contributions:

- We describe a nested Thomas cluster point process to model the locations of NG-RAN BSs. Our model serves as a benchmark for consuming partial location information by the LMF, which enables location-informed decisions built on the exciting new measurement capabilities offered by 3GPP Rel. 18+ B5G networks.
- We derive the distribution of the direct relative distance between a tagged UE and a target MEC host conditioned on the location information available at the LMF.
- We derive exact and approximate expressions for the joint distribution of distances between a tagged UE and two MEC hosts, enabling location-informed decisions involving multiple MEC hosts.
- We leverage our analysis and derive the service probability in MEC-enabled B5G network setups where partial location information is available by the LMF.

Section II introduces the paper notation and system model. Section III includes the performance analysis and Section IV the numerical results. Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a multi-tier cellular network (MTCN) NG-RAN infrastructure of N networking tiers, where each tier includes B5G BSs (gNBs) of similar technological capabilities and transmission profiles (e.g., range, MIMO antennas, measurement capabilities). We further consider that the locations of BSs within the MTCN infrastructure are modeled by a multi-tier *Nested Thomas Cluster Process* (NThCP) where the tier- $(n+1)$ BSs are clustered around some tier- n BSs, termed as the tier- n parent BSs in the sequel. It is not assumed that every tier- n BSs takes the role of a parent BS, i.e., the MTCN infrastructure is not assumed to form a balanced tree of BSs (in depth and width). Let Φ_{n+1} denote the point process (PP) describing the locations of tier- $(n+1)$ BSs, or equivalently, the union of all tier- $(n+1)$ BSs that are clustered around tier- n BSs, with $n \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$. The locations of all BSs in the MTCN infrastructure are included in $\Phi = \bigcup_{n=1}^N \Phi_n$. According to the NThCP [8], if a tagged

tier- $(n+1)$ cluster is centered around a tier- n BS $\mathbf{b}_i \in \Phi_n$ ($i \in \{1, \dots, |\Phi_n|\}$) then the BSs in the tagged cluster form a PP $M_{\mathbf{b}_i}^{n+1} = M_i^{n+1} + \mathbf{b}_i$, where \mathbf{b}_i also denotes the coordinates of the point in the Cartesian plane, the points in M_i^{n+1} are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d) and independently of the BS location \mathbf{b}_i , while the sets M_i^{n+1} are i.i.d and independently of the parent PP Φ_n . Also, the BSs of a tagged tier- $(n+1)$ cluster $M_{\mathbf{b}_i}^{n+1}$ are scattered independently around their parent BS $\mathbf{b}_i \in \Phi_n$ with variance σ_{n+1}^2 ; thus, their relative x and y coordinates (w.r.t. \mathbf{b}_i) are independent and distributed according to a normal distribution with zero mean and standard deviation σ_{n+1} .

The MTCN NG-RAN infrastructure performs standardized 3GPP measurements and reports them back sporadically to a centrally placed LMF module residing at the B5G network core, targeting to enable location-informed decisions on a system-wide scale. At minimum, the LMF maintains information on the locations of tier-1 BSs both in absolute Cartesian (X,Y) and in polar coordinate formats, e.g., by pulling such information from the OAM subsystem and converting their format in the ECEF coordinate system. The polar coordinates of a tier-1 BSs are composed by the relative distance and angle from the origin point $[0, 0]$ with respect to the direction towards true North and in a counter-clockwise fashion. All angle-focused location information by the LMF, is considered to use the same reference system (see Fig. 1). Without focusing on the particular logic that the LMF deploys to estimate location information, e.g., measurement patterns for sampling and/or conversion of the measurement time series to up-to-date estimates, we consider that the LMF processes the standard 3GPP measurements reported by BSs of lower tiers (i.e., $n > 1$) to infer on the relative polar coordinates of BSs with respect to their parent BSs. Such an approach is fully aligned with the scope of current 3GPP standards, where a large suite of measurement capabilities are provisioned to estimate the (relative) distance and angle from a tagged source to a target network node (Section I). Let \mathcal{J} denote the set of NG-RAN BSs, for which their relative polar coordinates with respect to their parent BS are known to the LMF. Since the locations of tier-1 BSs are always known to the LMF, by construction we get $\Phi_1 \subseteq \mathcal{J}$. We also consider that the LMF maintains knowledge of the standard deviation σ_n for all MTCN tiers, e.g., through collaboration with the OAM and NWDAF modules [5]. Thus, the full set of location information available at the LMF is summarized by $\{\mathcal{J}, \sigma_n \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}\}$. Our model does not consider any kind of multi-hop cellular communications across the NG-RAN tiers, e.g., through integrated-access backhaul - IAB. Instead, all BSs are considered to route the UEs' traffic directly through the B5G backhaul network by adhering to the management of the B5G network core functions.

Let us now focus on a tagged UE located at point \mathbf{u}_1 , which aims to assess its proximity to nearby MEC hosts towards offloading its edge-computing tasks. MEC hosts are assumed to be collocated with a subset of the NG-RAN BSs; however, not all NG-RAN BSs are collocated with a MEC host. We

Fig. 1. System Model

further focus in the practical scenario where the UE traffic is routed to the MEC server through the B5G backhaul network (and not directly through the NG-RAN) as follows: a) the UE u_1 forwards its traffic to its serving (parent) BS, b) the serving BS routes the UE traffic to the selected MEC host through the B5G network backhaul/core, e.g., in line with the local traffic breakout set up by the UPF, and c) the MEC host processes the UE's traffic to implement its requested edge-computing tasks and responds back with the outcome following a similar route. Although the communications between the tagged UE and the selected MEC host are performed through the backhaul network, the geographical distance separating the tagged UE u_1 with the MEC host is of paramount importance. In view of that, in the sequel, we do not assume that the UEs should be handed-off to the BS collocated with the selected MEC host, since we consider that a large separation distance between the UE and its serving BS would lead to severe interference in the NG-RAN and increased communication latency between the UE and the MEC host. Besides, as the UE moves within the MTCN NG-RAN infrastructure, minimizing the geographical distance between the UE and its serving MEC host mitigates the need for frequent MEC service migration to other hosts and minimize the probability of frequent service interruptions.

For analytical tractability, we focus on the scenario where the UE u_1 evaluates its proximity towards two available (target) MEC hosts: the MEC host #1 located at point h_1 and the MEC host #2 located at point h_2 . Future work targets to address the scenario of multiple MEC hosts. Let $Z_{1,1} = \|u_1 - b_{1,1}\|$ and $Z_{1,2} = \|u_1 - b_{2,1}\|$ be the relative Euclidean distance between the UE u_1 and the target MEC hosts h_1 and h_2 , respectively. Let $b_{u,n}^s$ denote the tier- n parent BS of the tagged UE u_1 (superscript s stands for source), where n runs down to the tier where the parent BS of UE u_1 lies into (e.g., in the example of Fig. 1, UE u_1 lies in tier-4 and its parent BS in tier-3). Similarly, let $b_{i,n}^t$ denote the tier- n parent BS of the MEC host h_i (superscript t

stands for target), where $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and n runs down to the tier where the MEC host resides (e.g., in the example of Fig. 1, host h_1 lies in tier-2 and host h_2 lies in tier-1). Our notation enables us to derive the joint statistics of the distances $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$ while accounting for the correlation introduced due to the overlapping topology across the UE to MEC host chains, e.g., shared location information/statistics for the parent BSs.

Without loss of generality, we place the tier-1 parent BS of UE u_1 at the origin of the Cartesian plane, i.e., $b_{1,1}^s = (0, 0)$ and take as $+x$ the direction towards the true North. Recall that all angles are measured with respect to the true North in a counter-clockwise fashion. Let $D_{1,i}$ denote the relative distance between the tier-1 parent BSs of the UE u_1 and MEC host h_i , and $\theta_{1,i}$ the angle formed from the tier-1 parent BS of user u_1 to the tier-1 parent BS of MEC host h_i according to our universal reference system (see Fig. 1). Since the LMF has full knowledge of the locations of tier-1 BSs, the pair values $(D_{1,i}, \theta_{1,i})$ are known at the LMF. By letting $D_{1,i}^x$ and $D_{1,i}^y$ denote the signed x-axis and y-axis components (projections) of the distance $D_{1,i}$, respectively, it follows that $D_{1,i}^x = D_{1,i} \cos(\theta_{1,i})$ and $D_{1,i}^y = D_{1,i} \sin(\theta_{1,i})$. Furthermore, since the BS locations are modeled according to the NThCP PP, it follows that $b_{u,n+1}^s = b_{u,n}^s + (X_{u,n+1}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s)$ where $X_{u,n+1}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s \sim N(0, \sigma_{n+1})$ are independent normal RVs with zero mean and same standard deviation σ_{n+1} . Similarly, $b_{i,n+1}^t = b_{i,n}^t + (X_{i,n+1}^t, Y_{i,n+1}^t)$ where $X_{i,n+1}^t, Y_{i,n+1}^t \sim N(0, \sigma_{n+1})$. Since $b_{1,1}^s = (0, 0)$, it readily follows that $b_{1,1}^t = (X_{1,1}^t = D_{1,1}^x, Y_{1,1}^t = D_{1,1}^y)$. In the general case, the LMF is unable to estimate the relative distances $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$, or the relative Cartesian coordinates $(X_{u,n+1}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s)$ and $(X_{i,n+1}^t, Y_{i,n+1}^t)$. However, the NG-RAN and the UEs provide relevant measurements to the LMF, the x and y-axis components $X_{1,n}^s, Y_{1,n}^s, X_{i,n}^t$ and $Y_{i,n}^t$ are derived as follows:

$$X_{1,n}^s = S_{1,n} \cos(\theta_{1,n}^s), Y_{1,n}^s = S_{1,n} \sin(\theta_{1,n}^s), \quad (1)$$

$$X_{i,n}^t = T_{i,n} \cos(\theta_{i,n}^t), Y_{i,n}^t = T_{i,n} \sin(\theta_{i,n}^t), \quad (2)$$

where i) the relative polar coordinates pair $(S_{1,n}, \theta_{1,n}^s)$ correspond to the estimated distance and angle between the tier- n and tier- $(n+1)$ parent BSs of user u_1 , and ii) the relative polar coordinates pair $(T_{i,n}, \theta_{i,n}^t)$ denotes the estimated distance and angle between the tier- n and tier- $(n+1)$ parent BSs of MEC host h_i . Recall that when the respective coordinates pair $(S_{1,n}, \theta_{1,n}^s)$ is available at the LMF then $b_{u,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}$. Similarly, if the coordinates pair $(T_{i,n}, \theta_{i,n}^t)$ is available at the LMF, then $b_{i,n}^t \in \mathcal{J}$. When the LMF has no knowledge of the respective relative polar coordinates pairs, the LMF can still encompass location information on the distribution of tier- $(n+1)$ BSs around their parent tier- n BS, by leveraging its knowledge of the standard deviation parameters σ_n . Besides, σ_{n+1} can also be viewed as the typical size of an error in the locations of tier- $(n+1)$ BSs around their tier- n parent BS, assuming a symmetric normal distribution around it. Accordingly, the NThCP model provides a practical benchmark for the deployment of location-informed network management, fully leveraging partial location knowledge constructed through the use of the

exciting new measurement capabilities supported by Rel. 18+ 3GPP standards. If the relative position of the UE \mathbf{u}_1 with respect to its serving BS is not known to the LMF, then we consider its position to be given by $\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{u},n}^s + (X_{1,u}^s, Y_{1,u}^s)$ where $X_{1,u}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s \sim N(0, \sigma_u)$ are independent normal RVs with zero mean and same standard deviation σ_u .

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Founded on the joint statistics of the distances $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$, a large suite of location-informed decisions can be made. To this end, in this section, we derive exact and approximate analytical expressions on both their individual and joint probability density function (pdf) and complementary cumulative density function (ccdf). We leverage our expressions to also derive the MEC service probability from at least one MEC host, given a maximum required distance threshold Z_{th} . In the sequel, we use the term the *UE's parent BS set* to refer to the collection of points that include the UE \mathbf{u}_1 and all of its parent BSs up to tier-1: $\mathbf{u}_1 \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s$. For notational convenience, in the sum, we run n up to N ; however, as discussed in Section II, we do not assume that a parent BSs at tier will always exist. In such occasions, we can eliminate the respective $\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s$ terms by setting them to \emptyset . Now, since the LMF may not have complete knowledge on the relative positions of all nodes in the *UE's parent BS set*, we use $\mathcal{J}_1^s \subseteq \mathcal{J}$ to denote the subset of nodes in $\mathbf{u}_1 \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s$ for which the LMF has location information knowledge, i.e., knowledge of their relative polar coordinates $(S_{1,n}, \theta_{1,n}^s)$ with respect to their parent BS.

Following a similar approach, we use the term the *MEC host's i parent BS set* to refer to the collection of points that include the MEC host \mathbf{h}_i and its parent BSs up to tier-1: $\mathbf{h}_i \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{i,n}^t$. Accordingly, we define as $\mathcal{J}_i^t \subseteq \mathcal{J}$ the subset of nodes in the *MEC host's i parent BS set* $\mathbf{h}_i \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{i,n}^t$ for which the LMF has location information knowledge, i.e., knowledge of their relative polar coordinates $(T_{i,n}, \theta_{i,n}^t)$ with respect to their parent BS. We also use the notation $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s$ and $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t$ to denote their complementary sets, respectively, such that $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s \cup \mathcal{J}_1^s = \mathbf{u}_1 \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s$ and $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t \cup \mathcal{J}_i^t = \mathbf{h}_i \cup_{n=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{i,n}^t$. Note that \mathcal{J} is a superset of both sets, as it includes location information for many users, NG-RAN BSs and MEC hosts. We now derive the pdf and ccdf of the distance $Z_{1,i}$ between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 (source) and a target MEC host \mathbf{h}_i (target).

Theorem 1. *The pdf $f_{Z_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z)$ of the distance $Z_{1,i}$ between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 and a target MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , conditioned on knowledge for the relative positions of the UE and NG-RAN nodes in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{J}_i^t , is Rice-distributed:*

$$f_{Z_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z) = \frac{z \cdot e^{-\frac{z^2 + (\alpha[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t])^2}{2(\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t])^2}}}{(\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t])^2} \cdot I_0 \left[\frac{z \cdot \alpha[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]}{(\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t])^2} \right], \quad (3)$$

where $I_0[x]$ denotes the modified Bessel function of the first kind and order zero, $\alpha[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$ is the non-centrality parameter of the Rice distribution that is constant and given by plugging $S = \mathcal{J}_1^s$ and $\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{J}_i^t$ in the following set of expressions:

$$\alpha[S, \mathcal{T}] = \sqrt{(\alpha^x[S, \mathcal{T}])^2 + (\alpha^y[S, \mathcal{T}])^2}, \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha^x[S, \mathcal{T}] = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in S} S_{1,k} \cos \theta_{1,k}^s - (D_{1,i}^x + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{T}} T_{i,q} \cos \theta_{i,q}^s), \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha^y[S, \mathcal{T}] = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in S} S_{1,k} \sin \theta_{1,k}^s - (D_{1,i}^y + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{T}} T_{i,q} \sin \theta_{i,q}^s), \quad (6)$$

and $\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t]$ is the scale parameter of the Rice distribution that is constant and given by plugging $\bar{S} = \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s$ and $\bar{\mathcal{T}} = \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t$ in the following expression:

$$\beta[\bar{S}, \bar{\mathcal{T}}] = \sqrt{\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in \bar{S}} (\sigma_k)^2 + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \bar{\mathcal{T}}} (\sigma_q)^2}. \quad (7)$$

The corresponding ccdf $\bar{F}_{Z_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z)$ is derived by

$$\bar{F}_{Z_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z) = Q_1 \left[\frac{\alpha[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]}{\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t]}, \frac{z}{\beta[\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s, \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t]} \right], \quad (8)$$

where $Q_1[a, b]$ denotes the Marcum-Q function of order one.

Proof. The proof can be readily derived by following a similar approach with [8]. We work on the right triangle formed by the sides $Z_{1,i}^x$, $Z_{1,i}^y$ and $Z_{1,i}$ (highlighted with red in Fig. 1 for each MEC host). Accordingly, the distance RV between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 and a target MEC host \mathbf{h}_i is given by $Z_{1,i} = \sqrt{(Z_{1,i}^x)^2 + (Z_{1,i}^y)^2}$, where the RVs $Z_{1,i}^x = |\mathbf{u}_1^x - \mathbf{h}_i^x|$ and $Z_{1,i}^y = |\mathbf{u}_1^y - \mathbf{h}_i^y|$ are independent and are governed by the x and y signed scalar projections of the relative position of all nodes in the *UE's* and the *MEC host's i parent BS sets*, respectively. In particular, $\mathbf{u}_1^x = \sum_{n \in \{u, 2, \dots, N\}} X_{1,n}^s$, $\mathbf{h}_i^x = D_{u,i}^x + \sum_{n=2}^N X_{i,n}^t$, $\mathbf{u}_1^y = \sum_{n \in \{u, 2, \dots, N\}} Y_{1,n}^s$ and $\mathbf{h}_i^y = D_{u,i}^y + \sum_{n=2}^N Y_{i,n}^t$. Note that the sums include i) constant values estimated as in Eqs. (1)-(2) for nodes with known relative positions at the LMF, i.e., nodes in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{J}_i^t , and ii) normally-distributed RVs with zero mean and known standard deviation(s) in $\{\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n\}$, which model the location of nodes with unknown relative positions to the LMF, i.e., nodes in $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s$ and $\bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t$. Accordingly, $Z_{1,i}^y$ and $Z_{1,i}^x$ are given by:

$$Z_{1,i}^x = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} X_{i,q}^t + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t} X_{i,q}^t \quad (9)$$

$$Z_{1,i}^y = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} Y_{i,q}^t + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t} Y_{i,q}^t \quad (10)$$

The two right summands in Eqs. (9)-(10) are constants that can be estimated by Eqs. (1)-(2) using the location knowledge at the LMF: \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{J}_i^t . Thus, the x and y signed scalar projections of $Z_{1,i}$ are independent and normally-distributed RVs with the same variance: $Z_{1,i}^x \sim N(\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} S_{1,k} \cos \theta_{1,k}^s - (D_{1,i}^x + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} T_{i,q} \cos \theta_{i,q}^s), \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} \sigma_k^2 + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t} \sigma_q^2)$ and $Z_{1,i}^y \sim N(\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} S_{1,k} \sin \theta_{1,k}^s - (D_{1,i}^y + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} T_{i,q} \sin \theta_{i,q}^s), \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,k}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} \sigma_k^2 + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_i^t} \sigma_q^2)$.

Accordingly, the RV $Z_{1,i} = \sqrt{(Z_{1,i}^x)^2 + (Z_{1,i}^y)^2}$ is Rice-distributed with i) non-centrality parameter given by the square

root of relative positions of nodes with known locations, and ii) scale parameter given by the square root of the summed variances governing the relative position of nodes with unknown locations. \square

We emphasize on the fact that the expressions in Eqs. (4)-(7) are constant values, which can be readily estimated at the LMF by leveraging location knowledge available in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{J}_i^t . We define them as a function of the argument sets \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{J}_i^t as their structure also appears in subsequent derivations. Since the union of the *UE's parent BS set* and the MEC hosts' *i parent BS sets* (which are now many) share BSs across the *UE and MEC host parent BS sets*, the incorporation of decision metrics that encompass comparisons between distance RVs $Z_{1,i}$ for multiple target MEC hosts still requires the joint distribution of $\{Z_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$. In our case, where the number of MEC hosts is two and thus, the shared network nodes across the end-to-end paths from the UE \mathbf{u}_1 to the target MEC hosts #1 and #2 will be consecutive. Fig. 1 provides an illustrative example where, although the MEC host #1 and #2 parent BS sets are disjoint, the distance RVs $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$ are still correlated due to their common *UE's parent BS set*.

We now focus on the scenario of two target MEC hosts. To better identify the shared part of the MTCN topology that creates correlation between the distance RVs $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$, we denote by $\mathcal{H}_0 = \mathcal{J}_1^t \cap \mathcal{J}_2^t$ the set of *shared* nodes across the two different MEC hosts paths to their tier-1 parents, for which the LMF *has knowledge* of their relative positions. Similarly, we denote by $\mathcal{G}_0 = \mathcal{J}_1^s \cap \mathcal{J}_2^s$ the set of *shared* nodes across the two different MEC hosts paths to their tier-1 parents, for which the LMF has *no knowledge* of their relative positions. Also, we define the sets $\mathcal{H}_1 = \mathcal{J}_1^t \setminus \mathcal{H}_0$ and $\mathcal{H}_2 = \mathcal{J}_2^t \setminus \mathcal{H}_0$ that include *non-shared* nodes across the MEC host #1 and #2 path to their tier-1 parents, respectively, for which the LMF *has knowledge* of their relative positions. Similarly, we define the sets $\mathcal{G}_1 = \mathcal{J}_1^s \setminus \mathcal{G}_0$ and $\mathcal{G}_2 = \mathcal{J}_2^s \setminus \mathcal{G}_0$ that include *non-shared* nodes across the MEC host #1 and #2 paths to their tier-1 parents, respectively, for which the LMF *has no knowledge* of their relative positions. We now derive the joint pdf/ccdf of the distance RVs $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$.

Theorem 2. *The joint pdf $f_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2)$ of the distances $Z_{1,1}$, $Z_{1,2}$ between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 and the two target MEC hosts \mathbf{h}_1 , \mathbf{h}_2 , respectively, conditioned on knowledge for the relative positions of the UE and NG-RAN nodes in \mathcal{J} , is expressed by Eq. (11), where the constants $\alpha^x[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$, $\alpha^y[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$ and $\beta[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$ are given by Eqs. (5)-(7). Their joint ccdf $\bar{F}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2)$ is given by Eq. (12).*

Proof. We observe that the correlation between the RVs $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$ comes from the relative positions of MTCN nodes in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{G}_0 , i.e., the set of shared nodes across the UE to MEC hosts' *i paths* for which the LMF has no knowledge of their relative positions. In view of that, we first derive the conditional distribution of the distance RVs $Z_{1,1}$, $Z_{1,2}$ conditioned on fixed values for the relative position of nodes in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{G}_0 , and then marginalize the respective conditional

distribution with respect to the joint distribution of the relative positions of nodes in \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{G}_0 (law of total probability).

Let us define the auxiliary RVs $W_{1,i} = \sqrt{(W_{1,i}^x)^2 + (W_{1,i}^y)^2}$ where $W_{1,i}^x$ and $W_{1,i}^y$ are given by Eqs. (13)-(14). Note that the RVs $W_{1,i}^x$, $W_{1,i}^y$ are of similar structure with the ones in Eq. (9)-(10), respectively; however, Eqs. (13)-(14) consider that the relative positions of shared MTCN nodes in the sets \mathcal{J}_1^s and \mathcal{G}_0 are now fixed. Accordingly, conditioned on the originally given and (now) assumed location knowledge at the LMF, the RVs $W_{1,i}^x$, $W_{1,i}^y$ are conditionally independent and normally-distributed with the same variance: $W_{1,i}^x \sim N(X + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} X_{i,q}^t, \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} \sigma_q)$ and $W_{1,i}^y \sim N(Y + \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} Y_{i,q}^t, \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{J}_i^t} \sigma_q)$, where the (constant) values of X and Y are expressed by:

$$X = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_0} X_{i,q}^t, \quad (15)$$

$$Y = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_0} Y_{i,q}^t. \quad (16)$$

By following a similar approach with our proof in Theorem 1, it can be readily shown that the distribution of the RVs $W_{1,i}$, conditioned on constant X and Y values, is Rice-distributed with non-centrality parameter (constant) as shown below:

$$\alpha_i^w = \sqrt{(a^x[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + X)^2 + (a^y[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + Y)^2} \quad (17)$$

and scale parameter $\beta_i^w = \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_i} (\sigma_q)^2$ (constant), or equivalently $\beta_i^w = \beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i]$, where $a^x[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$, $a^y[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t]$ and $\beta_i^w = \beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i]$ are derived by Eqs. (5)-(7). Accordingly, the joint pdf of the RVs $\{Z_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ can be derived by:

$$\begin{aligned} & f_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2) = \\ \stackrel{a}{=} & \iint_{(x,y) \in \mathbb{R}^2} f_{X,Y}(x,y) \cdot f_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}, X, Y}(z_1, z_2) dx dy \\ \stackrel{b}{=} & \iint_{(x,y) \in \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2(\beta[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0])^2}}}{2\pi\beta[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0]^2} f_{W_{1,1}, W_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}, X, Y}(z_1, z_2) dx dy \\ \stackrel{c}{=} & \iint_{(x,y) \in \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2(\beta[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0])^2}}}{2\pi\beta[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0]^2} \cdot \prod_{i \in \{1,2\}} f_{W_{1,i} | \mathcal{J}, X, Y}(z_i) dx dy \end{aligned}$$

where step (a) follows by conditioning the joint pdf of $\{Z_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ on fixed values for the RVs X, Y that insert correlation and marginalizing the probability density over their state space using the law of total probability; step (b) follows by construction of the X, Y RVs in Eqs. (15)-(16), which involve sums of independent and normally-distributed RVs with zero-mean yet known variance, and by taking into account that the joint distribution of the RVs $\{Z_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$, conditioned on knowledge of X, Y , is described by the joint distribution of the auxiliary RVs $\{W_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ given the constant values of X, Y ; and step (c) follows from the fact that

$$f_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2) = \iint_{(x,y) \in \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{e\left(-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2(\beta[\bar{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0])^2}\right)}{2\pi\beta[\bar{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0]^2} \prod_{i \in \{1,2\}} \frac{z_i \cdot I_0 \left[\frac{z_i \cdot \sqrt{(ax[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + x)^2 + (ay[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + y)^2}}{(\beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i])^2} \right]}{(\beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i])^2 \cdot e^{\frac{z_i^2 + (ax[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + x)^2 + (ay[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + y)^2}{2(\beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i])^2}}} dx dy \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{F}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2) = \iint_{(x,y) \in \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{e\left(-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2(\beta[\bar{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0])^2}\right)}{2\pi\beta[\bar{J}_1^s, \mathcal{G}_0]^2} \prod_{i \in \{1,2\}} Q_1 \left[\frac{\sqrt{(ax[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + x)^2 + (ay[\mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t] + y)^2}}{\beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i]}, \frac{z}{\beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i]} \right] dx dy \quad (12)$$

$$W_{1,i}^x = \underbrace{\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{H}_0} X_{i,q}^t - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{H}_i} X_{i,q}^t}_{\text{Known relative positions to the LMF}} + \underbrace{\left(\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} X_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_0} X_{i,q}^t \right) - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_i} X_{i,q}^t}_{\substack{\text{Shared-node positions assumed to be fixed} \\ \text{Unknown relative positions to the LMF}}} \quad (13)$$

$$W_{1,i}^y = \underbrace{\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \mathcal{J}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{H}_0} Y_{i,q}^t - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{H}_i} Y_{i,q}^t}_{\text{Known relative positions to the LMF}} + \underbrace{\left(\sum_{\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s \in \bar{\mathcal{J}}_1^s} Y_{1,n}^s - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_0} Y_{i,q}^t \right) - \sum_{\mathbf{b}_{i,q}^t \in \mathcal{G}_i} Y_{i,q}^t}_{\substack{\text{Shared-node positions assumed to be fixed} \\ \text{Unknown relative positions to the LMF}}} \quad (14)$$

the auxiliary RVs $\{W_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ are conditionally independent (given the constant values of X, Y) as they are composed by independent and normally-distributed RVs with the same variance (i.e., by construction of the NThCP-based MTCN model). Since the individual RVs $\{W_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ have been shown to be Rice-distributed with non-centrality parameter given by Eq. (17) and scale $\beta_i^w = \beta[\emptyset, \mathcal{G}_i]$, we conclude with the expression in Eq. (11). By using a similar approach with in steps (a)-(c), but working with the respective ccdf (instead of pdf) expressions of the conditionally independent Rice-distributed $\{W_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ RVs, we can readily derive the joint ccdf expression for $\{Z_{1,i}\}_{i \in \{1,2\}}$ in Eq. (12). Note that all derivations assume $\mathcal{G}_i \neq \emptyset$, or else special cases apply. \square

Corollary 1. *The joint pdf $f_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2)$ and ccdf $\bar{F}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2)$ can be approximated by:*

$$\tilde{f}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2) = \prod_{i \in \{1,2\}} \tilde{f}_{Z_{1,i} | \mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z_i) \quad (18)$$

$$\tilde{\bar{F}}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(z_1, z_2) = \prod_{i \in \{1,2\}} \tilde{\bar{F}}_{Z_{1,i} | \mathcal{J}_1^s, \mathcal{J}_i^t}(z_i) \quad (19)$$

Proof. It readily follows by Theorem 1, by assuming independence between the two distance RVs $Z_{1,1}$ and $Z_{1,2}$. \square

Corollary 2. *The service probability of a tagged UE in a MEC-enabled B5G network where i) the LMF has partial knowledge of the relative positions of the UE and NG-RAN nodes in \mathcal{J} , ii) the UE is in proximity of two available MEC hosts, and iii) a maximum distance threshold Z_{th} is required to attain service continuity between the tagged UE and any MEC host, can be readily estimated by:*

$$\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{J}}[Z_{th}] = 1 - \bar{F}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(Z_{th}, Z_{th}). \quad (20)$$

Proof. The outage probability is defined by the event where none of the two available MEC hosts are within proximity,

i.e., within the maximum required distance Z_{th} . The specific measure can be readily estimated by $\bar{F}_{Z_{1,1}, Z_{1,2} | \mathcal{J}}(Z_{th}, Z_{th})$; thus, its complement derives the service probability. \square

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section validates the accuracy of the derived analytical results in Section III, assesses the performance gap between exact / approximate expressions and draws valuable insights on how the service probability performance can be improved in NG-RAN setups with an LMF deployed. All of our results consider an MTCN layout similar to our system model in Fig. 1. Thus, both MEC hosts are placed at tier #2 while the UE at tier #4. Unless differently stated, we set $\sigma_1 = 500, \sigma_2 = 250, \sigma_3 = 100, \sigma_4 = 50$ and, depending on the location information available at the LMF, we focus on the following scenarios of high practical interest:

- **Scenario 1 (S1).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations $\mathcal{J}_1 = \{b_{1,1}^s, b_{1,1}^t, b_{2,1}^t\}$.
- **Scenario 2 (S2).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations and the tier-2 parent BS of the UE: $\mathcal{J}_2 = \mathcal{J}_1 \cup \{b_{1,2}^s\}$.
- **Scenario 3 (S3).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations and the tier-2/-3 parent BS of the UE: $\mathcal{J}_3 = \mathcal{J}_2 \cup \{b_{1,3}^s\}$.

Fig. 2 plots the MEC Service Probability $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{J}}$, as calculated by Corollary 2 assuming either the *Exact* joint ccdf expression derived by Theorem 2, or the *Approximate* joint ccdf expression derived by Corollary 1, for all scenarios under scope. In the same plot, we also draw the frequency (percentage) of events where the MTCN topology leads to a service event (red line), i.e., $\mathbf{1}(Z_{1,1} \leq Z_{th} \vee Z_{1,2} \leq Z_{th})$ termed as *Ground Truth*. We further draw the MEC service probability assuming only one MEC host, by substituting the ccdf expression for MEC host #1 from Theorem 1 in Corollary 2. All the results of Fig. 2 are averaged over 10.000 random MTCN topology samples. We start our discussion by observing that the MEC

Fig. 2. Monte-Carlo (10K): Service Probability vs. distance threshold

service probability as estimated by the *exact* expressions (Theorem 2), almost matches the frequency of MEC service events as measured in (and averaged over) 10,000 random MTCN topologies that were generated using Monte Carlo sampling. This result validates our analysis, also through simulations, provided that averaging the results of our analysis over a very large number of MTCN samples is equivalent to removing the bias introduced by a particular network setup (or relevant knowledge at the LMF) while maintaining the statistics of the entire MTCN structure; this also explains why the *Ground Truth* results match the exact expressions under the S1 setup.

Interestingly, Fig. 2 also demonstrates that, for a given distance threshold Z_{th} and scenario of LMF knowledge, our expressions can be readily used to estimate the service probability increase due to the presence of an additional MEC host. This follows by comparing the results of the *Exact* expressions for two MEC hosts (joint statistics) with that for one MEC host. In particular, Fig. 2 demonstrates that for all scenarios under scope, i.e., independently of the knowledge available at the LMF, the presence of two instead of one MEC hosts increase the MEC service probability by roughly 25% in an absolute scale for the same distance threshold Z_{th} (vertically). On the other hand, for a given MEC service probability target (horizontally), e.g., $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{J}} = 0.8$, the presence of one additional MEC host enables the UE to relax the requirement of having a maximum distance threshold for service Z_{th} , by up to 1km, i.e., if seamless MEC service migration can be assumed between MEC hosts and adequate knowledge is available.

Another notable result in Fig. 2 is that, on the average, i.e., averaged over a large number of Monte Carlo samples, the *exact* and *approximate* expressions of Corollary 1 provide roughly the same MEC service probability estimate. Thus, in the long-term, the use of approximate (instead of exact) expressions can provide acceptable accuracy towards location-informed decisions. Nonetheless, as depicted in Fig. 3, the use of the approximate expressions can also lead to notable estimation errors under specific NG-RAN setups, especially in the presence of more fine-grained location knowledge at the

Fig. 3. $\mathcal{J} = \{b_{1,2}^s = (50, 100), b_{1,3}^s = (80, 80), b_{1,u}^s = (-40, 30), b_{1,1}^t = (-100, 150), b_{1,1}^t = (80, 100), b_{2,1}^t = (300, 100), b_{2,2}^t = (-50, 50)\}$

LMF ($S_3 \rightarrow S_1$). This follows by comparing the $\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{J}}$ using the *exact* and *approximate* expressions under scenarios S_2 , where the estimation error is non-negligible, and S_3 , where the estimation error limits up to 100% in the low Z_{th} regime, i.e., when the MEC mobility management requirements are tighter. This highlights the importance of deploying location-informed decisions that consume knowledge conditioned on the joint distribution of NG-RAN/MEC host locations.

V. CONCLUSION

We constructed an analytical NThCP-based model to enable location-informed network management through the consumption of NG-RAN measurements. We have derived the joint distribution of distances between a tagged UE and two available MEC hosts and used them to assess the MEC service probability in MEC-enabled NG-RAN infrastructures. Numerical results provided valuable yet measurable insights on key performance trade-offs. Future work aims to extend our analysis in multi-MEC host setups and further leverage the derived result of the joint direct distance distributions.

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